

LAÏCITÉ UNDER PRESSURE: FROM THE HEADSCARF BAN TO THE ANTI-SEPARATISM BILL AND MUSLIM INTEGRATION

Anas Perooly

Research Scholar, European Studies
School of International Studies,
Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi
panashanan@gmail.com

Abstract

This paper will explore the different aspects of the Muslim question in France regarding their integration into French society. After the world war, Europe witnessed an influx of migrant populations to Western Europe, particularly France, but the debate over their integration has attracted much scholarly attention. The French secular law, *laïcité*, has been at the front of integration discourse, and the headscarf ban was legitimised under the law. France has also witnessed many terrorist attacks, and the Charlie Hebdo killing was the most brutal event that ignited the question of the compatibility of the values of immigrants with those of the French regarding freedom of expression and liberty. The article discusses the various responses after the attack and examines the shift in the narratives, which further alienated the Muslim minority by conflating Islam and terrorism. The presence and development of radical Islam are also discussed in order to investigate the various aspects of the Muslim question in France. After the murder of Samuel Paty, Emmanuel Macron introduced the Anti-separatism Bill, which has a profound impact on Muslim lives in perpetuating otherness and exacerbating tensions among minority groups in terms of mobility and visibility. I argue that recognising minority rights and adopting the necessary steps to tackle discrimination is inevitable to integrate Muslims into French society. Both Muslim leadership and the government would take the measures required to make the most significant minority of the republic feel like French.

Keywords: French Muslims, Hijab Ban, Laïcité, Anti-Separatism Bill, Religious Discrimination

Introduction

Europe underwent massive destruction in the Second World War (1939–1945). Some cities, historical monuments, and industrial sites have been

partially destroyed or disappeared. The social, political, economic, and cultural scenarios were not the same before the war. So, the reconstruction of Europe was inevitable, and it could not be done without a massively cheap labour force. First waves of immigrants came to Europe between 1950 and 1970, with France and Britain witnessing a large influx in the 1950s. This flow of immigrants continued to form a bulk of the immigrant population in Western countries. (Rudnicka-Kassem 2016) Consequently, between 1950 and 1970, the number of Muslim immigrants substantially increased. Due to the impossibility of returning to their home country for various complicated reasons, immigrants settled in Europe, starting families and making plans for their future in Europe.

The French colonial empire ruled several Muslim countries from the early ninetieth till the mid-twentieth century. At the end of the colonial period, the Muslim population in the French mainland increased. The only public evidence of Islam in French urban spaces is the Paris Mosque, constructed by the French state to commemorate Muslim soldiers who served the French army in the Second World War. (Fredette, 2014)

However, contemporary French Muslims have been asked to show their allegiance to their host country while the law and other institutional mechanisms hinder their integration into French society by creating many constraints that prevent them from feeling like French citizens. The growing populism and the political shift into conservatism also created new problems for Muslims in the wake of the terrorist attacks that shook Europe. One of the deadliest terrorist attacks was on Charlie Hebdo. The government introduced the new bill, popularly known as the Anti-separatism Bill, which observed Muslims and Islamic organisations in the country as a tool to infiltrate religious affairs and arbitrarily control the function of Islamic activities. Besides these laws, banning the headscarf also posed an identity crisis for Muslims, as many believe the scarf is an essential religious practice in Islam. However, the ongoing debate on integration further pushed the community into an unprecedented identity crisis.

The Muslim Minority in France

The Muslim presence in Europe is visible as Islam is the second religion after Christianity in France, thanks to the significant increase in the

Muslim population in Western Europe with 15 million Muslims. Many Muslims adopted European nationality and participated in professional associations and other religious organisations. Due to the high birth rate and newcomers with refugee status, the population increased rapidly, apart from the converts to Islam. Many other Muslims are coming to Europe to study and have a temporary stay. The visibility of Muslim presence in Europe has been changing for the last two decades. There are numerous Islamic organisations and cultural centres where Muslims can feel a sense of belonging to their religious identity. Countries like France, Great Britain, and Germany, with a sizeable Muslim population, have thousands of official Islamic organisations. (Downing 2019)

The Muslim identity among Muslims worldwide, including in Europe, can be classified as ethnic, cultural, and religious. Ethnic Muslims are not practising Islam, but they are born into Muslim families with basic knowledge about religion and not much attached to their ethnic tradition. The Muslims are linked to Islamic culture rooted in religious symbols and showing much allegiance to the universal dimension of Islam. Even though they have different political ideologies, they are tied up with powerful cultural elements. The third category is religious Muslims, with solid sentiments toward the Muslim Ummah. They are very keen on practices like five daily prayers and fulfilling their religious obligations. Some may affiliate with different spiritual and mystical orders, while others engage in missionary activities. The fundamentalists believe Islam is not only a religion but it should be a political system in all parts of the world for the emancipation of humanity. They are the supreme responsibility for the negative image of Islam across Europe. (Downing 2019)

There was no other public evidence of Islam in the secular urban spaces. However, Muslims began to build mosques in France as the population increased substantially. The five mosques in 1965 reached 1020 in 1990; in 2004, the number increased to 1685. Instead, the Muslim population in France reached four to five million, constituting 7-8 per cent of the population. (Rudnicka-Kassem 2016)

The Trajectory of Laïcité

Laïcité is the French way of secularism that forbids religious intervention in state affairs. It was enshrined as a law to get rid of the considerable influence of the Roman Catholic church and the monarchy

alike. The law was enacted in 1905 and was developed during the French Revolution, which acted as a shield against the exploitation of organised religion in the state administration and the public institutions. In the early twentieth century, France was a homogenous country with a substantial Christian population, and Laïcité implied the separation of state from the church. However, after the Second World War and the subsequent decolonisation, France witnessed an influx of immigrants from different parts of the world, particularly from her erstwhile colonies like Morocco and Algeria, primarily Muslim-populated countries. The insistence on Laïcité after the evolution of France from a homogenous Christian community to a heterogeneous and multireligious society created more tension among the minority religious groups, particularly Muslims. They observed the law as an injunction to shed the layers of their religious identity. Thus, Laïcité, instead of becoming a legal tool to protect diversity and ethnic-religious rights, became a tool to disown the minorities from the French mainstream society. (Webster, 2007)

Inspired by the philosophy of separation propagated by Laïcité, the French government banned religious symbols like headscarves, crosses and kippa in public schools in 2004. Moreover, in 2010, the government further banned the Burqa from the public sphere. Nevertheless, such restrictions exacerbated the tension among minorities, especially Muslims, and the ban resulted in massive demand for Muslim private schools, culminating in segregation and the disintegration of the former. However, right-wing politicians indicated the burgeoning number of schools as a real threat to French values and alleged that Muslims tend to remain in seclusion deliberately and live a parallel life (Webster, 2007)

After the Charlie Hebdo attack, the government incorporated laïcité into the public schools' curriculum. The French president then called laïcité non-negotiable, and the move was inspired when a chunk of the students denied their participation in one-minute mourning for the victims killed in the Charlie Hebdo attack after publishing the cartoons insulting Prophet Muhammed

Benoist Apparou, a French legislator, called the new French secular norm based upon Laïcité secular totalitarianism after the enormous dystopian consequences of Laïcité that dismantled the religious minorities. The French government is very reluctant to conduct a survey on the socio-

economic conditions of the migrants so that the administration can make a viable approach to find the remedies for their backwardness and subsequently integrate them. Jonathan Laurence, a fellow at the Brookings Institution, points out that such an indifferent attitude of the government will perpetuate the structural discrimination of the immigrants and increase the tendency of disintegration. The absence of data regarding the various aspects of immigrants in France hampers the formation of policies to let them integrate into the mainstream (Laurence 2011)

A 1978 law expressly prohibits the collection of data that reveals an individual's religious and ethnic identity, leaving no official statistics to investigate social discrimination against minority groups. The absence of official data overlooked the backwardness of the immigrants in the country, and the courts interpreted the law as a source of prohibition of any religious affiliation in the public sphere. (Gilbert, Keane 2016) The principle of equality is also implied in the prohibition of data collection on ethnic and religious grounds, which means there is no adequate data to rely on the discrimination of immigrants, particularly Muslims, Africans, and Romas. The questions regarding race and ethnicity are excluded from the national census, and the socio-economic status of the marginalised people is disappeared by the state apparatus.

The result of this total absolute equality and subsequent efforts by the government to not recognise the discrimination of minorities exacerbated the tensions in French society. Another ramification was the indifference of the French government to forging a public policy exclusively for immigrants to resolve discrimination and inequality. Instead, anti-discrimination policies further mention the concerned population as immigrants, even though they belong to the third or fourth generation. (Gilbert, Keane 2016). The hate speeches targeting immigrants are not documented or reported despite many efforts employed by the government to tackle and monitor the public incitement to hatred in the wake of the terrorist attack in 2015.

The Headscarf Debate

In 1989, the ban on the headscarf was implemented in France, and the feminist discourse supported it. They argued that the veil symbolises women's oppression and gender inequality vis-a-vis the men. The republican discourse also backed the headscarf ban, noting that it would

bring a sense of communitarianism and ghettoisation. The defenders of the ban pointed out that the education institutions should act as "a place of liberation" and that religious and communitarian symbols should not be permitted. In November 1989, the state council issued that the wearing of religious signs is not incompatible with the principle of secularism. Furthermore, it was allowed on the condition that such symbols would not disturb the functioning of the educational institutions. After the promulgation of the law in 2004, local courts permitted students wearing headscarves to enter the school or return to the institutions. Among the Forty-nine cases that reached the council's consideration between 1992 and 1999, only one point was upheld against the student due to the overwhelming protests from the parents and students threatening the public order. Though the ban was severely criticised by Muslim organisations and proponents of the pluralistic secularists, some organisations like Conseil Français des musulmans laïques (CFML, French Council of Secular Muslims) supported the ban. (Laurence & Viasse 2007).

Another implication of the ban was the coalition between the rightists and the leftists. For the rightists, the primary threat was immigration rooted in Islamophobia; hence, they supported leftists in their demand to ban the headscarf. After the 2002 presidential election, President Chirac appointed a commission with twenty members to look into the issue. Most of the members were selected from the combative secularists. The report submitted by the commission demanded a ban on school students' religious signs. The president severely criticised and blamed the religious symbols, alleging they would cause disunity and sow the seeds of communitarianism in the public education spaces. Another commission appointed by Jean Louis Debre, the national assembly president, submitted a report that revealed that the headscarves have nothing to do with religion but the manifestation of pressure exerted by the family and society.

However, many scholars rejected these two reports, especially that of Dobre, due to their monolithic portrayal of the headscarf as a mere symbol of women's oppression. They countered such depictions by stressing that the headscarf implies the desire for integration without assimilation and faith and belief, a feeling of cultural identity with Islam and self-identification. In 2004, the French parliament passed a legislative bill calling for the ban on students' display of religious

symbols in public schools, with an overwhelming majority in the national assembly and the senate. It was followed by the expulsion of forty-seven Muslim students from the public schools, while many Muslim students either shifted to private schools or left education. Some students went to school in another country.

The Charlie Hebdo attack

The Charlie Hebdo attack sparked more debates regarding Islamic fundamentalism, with the political narratives surrounding it heated up, and media reports criticised Islam as not compatible with French values in terms of freedom of expression and religious freedom. The office of the satirical magazine was attacked on January 07 2015, by two armed people, killing 12 people. The media reported, quoting eyewitnesses, that the gunmen shouted: "We have avenged the prophet Muhammed" and "Allahu Akbar" since Charlie Hebdo was planning to publish some cartoons of the prophet Mohammed (BBC 2015). A series of attacks followed the event; after two days, a gunman killed a policewoman, and another armed man, namely Amedy Coulibaly, took many people hostage, at a supermarket in Porte de Vincennes in eastern Paris after starting a shootout. He threatened to shoot the hostages unless the perpetrators of the Charlie Hebdo attack, Cherif Kouachi and Said Kouachi, were allowed to be free. However, the French security force killed all three gunmen. After that, Al-Qaida in the Arabian Peninsula (AQAP) claimed responsibility for the attack. (BBC 2015).

François Hollande, then the French president, condemned the attack and called for the support of the people to come together against terrorism and vanguard democracy, freedom and pluralism. The former French president, Nicholas Sarkozy, decried the attack vehemently, stating that the attack was against civilisation and urging people to join hands against "barbarism". Similarly, people worldwide extended their solidarity and condemned the terrorist attack on press freedom and liberty. In France, people from different walks of society gathered together to show their solidarity with Charlie Hebdo. The French phrase "Je Suis Charlie" (Me too Charlie) supported the magazine and defended the right to free expression. Many world leaders participated in massive rallies across the country, creating an atmosphere of unity and empathy. The next day, thousands of people identified as Patriotic Europeans Against the Islamization of the West (PEGIDA) rallied in Dresden

against the attack. French President Hollande denounced the linking of the attack with Muslims, while Marine Le Pen criticised and held Islamic fundamentalism as the primary motive, stating that the ideology behind terrorism has its roots on French soil.

The political leaders of European Union member states also extended their solidarity with France. Angela Merkel, then German Chancellor, rejected the anti-Islam rallies led by PEGIDA, explicitly saying that Islam belongs to Germany and that the country is doing its best to integrate the migrants into German society regardless of their ethnicity. (Ghouse 2015) The EU response was somewhat similar to that of Sarkozy and Le Pen (Sahill 2017). Dimitris Avramopoulos, the EU commissioner for immigration and home affairs, said that Europe should protect its values against those who hate democracy and the European way of life and urged EU member states to adopt the necessary steps to curb money laundering that finances radicalisation and collect the passengers' data. (Avramopoulos 2015).

At a meeting of the foreign ministers of EU member states after the event, it was decided to launch an anti-terror project to curb further terrorist attacks. In her media briefing, the EU foreign policy chief, Federica Mogherini, stressed the importance of improving communication with the population within the EU and beyond. (Mogherini 2015). The response of the EU and non-EU political leaders after the terrorist attack could be seen as an assault on freedom of expression; later, when it came to the policy level, the narrative was combined with terrorism, and EU member countries decided to adopt security measures. The discourse eventually shifted to the issue of identity/difference, as evidenced by political statements by EU leaders and media reports. (Sahill 2017) The statements of Mogherini create an "us" and "other" dichotomy and might result in alienating the Arabic-speaking other from the European self. The dividing practices influence the public imagination of the Arabic-speaking population and give power to the authorities to intervene in the matters of the community since EU members have agreed to send security personnel to the population to prevent money laundering that finances terrorist activities. The creation of this binary also helps the EU intentionally blanket its flaws and the discrepancies in its system. (Sahill 2017)

In Marine Le Pen's response, the dichotomy she represents is two-fold. The first one is the French self, which is essentially in danger posed by the 'Islamist migrant other', and the second one is the 'French self', which is threatened and shaken by the violence and fundamentalism since it is part of the EU other, a system overwhelmed by discrepancies. She reiterates that the solution is to stop immigration and freeze the Schengen agreement. The comments of Sarkozy imply the clash of civilisations (Huntington 1996) and create the notion of a civilised and barbaric fold that remains in conflict regarding values. The political ideology of Islamic militants influenced the culprits of the attack. Their act of violence was aimed not only at killing the journalist and cartoonist who committed the blasphemy by drawing the cartoons of the prophet Muhammed but also at making a more significant division between 'them' and 'us' based on the concept of Ummah. This concept makes all Muslims a nation irrespective of their ethnicity, colour, race, geographical location, and religion, which would be the only binding identity. (Sahill 2017)

The media has played an essential role in interlinking Islam with attacks, thus diminishing the issue into the religious discourse and escaping from the Muslim question in France regarding discrimination and state indifference. Media narratives like the presence of dangerous armed soldiers of Muslim communities prepared for deadly terror attacks being trained overseas by international terrorist organisations further alienate French Muslims and do not explain the problem fully (Fredette, 2014). Another implication is the growing public perception that Islam is an impending threat to France. As a result, Muslims are imagined as undeserving citizens or partially French and not fit for the republic. The discrimination and the terrorist attacks perpetuate the Muslim immigrants as hostile 'other'.

Islamic Radicalism

The radicalisation of European Muslims is not a consequence of Middle Eastern events, but the discrimination prevailing on the continent in terms of employment, education, housing, and health should be taken into account. Remarkably, Muslims of North African descent are more vulnerable to marginalisation and inequalities. (Yahya 2015). As a consequence of this marginalisation, the pean cities have witnessed the emergence of Muslim gangs. Simultaneously, there are educated young

Muslims who have been educated in Europe, are employed, and have quickly found their space in European society. Also, Muslims actively participate in Islamic activities, seeking social and political mobility. However, only a tiny minority within the community wants to be a part of the terrorist activities and end up through the means of violence. The history of Europe, along with its legal structure and policies, creates varying barriers for Muslim individuals and organisations to integrate into European society (Nielson 2007). As far as the French Muslim immigrants are concerned, the French government has to recognise the religious rights and cultural demands of their most significant minority (Hamel 2002).

The presence of political Islam in Europe could be traced back to the late 80s and the early 90s as an outcome of political events in the Middle East (video 2011). The former Afghan jihadis who fought against the Soviet Union and other militant groups arrived in Europe to escape political repression and build their bases in Europe. The extensive networks of the diaspora and the favoured conditions in terms of freedom and economic conditions helped them continue their activities despite the geographical distance. Since authorities were unaware that these networks were being consolidated at the local level, radical organisations could continue operating without the security agencies' notice. Even though they created a strong base and a chain of communication with hierarchies of command, Europe was not the target of the militant groups but an asylum in which they could remain unnoticed and finance their activities.

When Osama Bin Laden established Al-Qaida, it marked the second phase of the advent of radical Islam in Europe, and the translational potential of the organisation culminated in the unity of militant organisations across the globe, vowing to attack the secular governments in the Muslim world and the western countries that protect those regimes. After the 9/11 attack, Al-Qaida was severely hit by the American attack; nevertheless, the transnational networks and the individual affiliations with the different groups remained resilient. Many terrorists trained in the tribal areas of Pakistan and returned to Europe and the USA to carry out their attacks. (Vidino, 2011).

While recognising the conflict between European and Muslim civilisations emanating from historical events, European Muslims are

looking for a free space of Islam within Europe with their belief in transnational Islam that informs the actions of the people and the worldview. (Tibi 2008). According to political Islam, the notion of a state shaped by the Westphalian order is contested, and European Muslims should have their allegiance to the imagined Ummah rather than the European citizenry. (Tibi, 2008).

Anti-separatism Bill and Emmanuel Macron

After the Samuel Paty killing, the discourse of international terrorism and home-grown radicalisation intertwined, and the government introduced a bill titled "Strengthening Respect for Republican Values", widely known as the Anti-Separatism Bill. A Chechen student beheaded Paty after displaying cartoons of the prophet Mohammed in a class on freedom of expression. After the incident, the French government immediately deported 200 Imams accused of radicalisation and closed many mosques allegedly associated with the primary source of the dissemination of hatred and separatism. (Käsehage,2021)To get away from the accusation of Islamophobia, the Anti-Separatism Bill does not mention the name of Islam or Muslims, but the statement "what we need to tackle is Islamist Separatism, the French president is a clear indicator that the target is Muslims.

The evolution of Macron from the image of a central liberalist to an Islamophobic conservative is a ramification of the French political shift to the right due to the massive demand from the public for stringent adherence to law and order. Similarly, the economic crisis in the wake of COVID-19 and the terrorist attacks have tremendously affected Macron's popularity, resulting in losing the majority of his original electorate. As the election is going to happen in 2002, the political strategy of Macron is likely to pander to the conservative votes of Marine Le Pen, his primary opponent and the leader of the far-right National Front party.

According to the bill, If hate speech is reported, authorities are allowed to close any place of worship for up to two months and impose penalties. The convicted people in the terrorist cases would be banned from leading any religious association for ten years. The bill extended the exhibition of religious symbols in the public sphere and legitimised the neutrality principle of the state. It will prohibit public servants from wearing religious clads like the Hijab and expressing political views.

The law is also applicable to the employees of private contractors in the public service. The bill confers the power on the government authorities to dissolve any religious organisation, after which the Collective Against Islamophobia in France, a well-known Muslim NGO, was disbanded under charges of carrying out Islamic propaganda. French Interior Minister Gerald Darmanin declared the official dissolution after the meeting of the Council of Ministers. The dissolution could be carried out by decree without a prior judicial inquiry into the association of the organisation with radical groups or indulging in separatist activities.

If any organisation needs public funds, signing a Republican Contract is mandatory to abide by the terms and conditions. The rule also provides the executive power to suspend Islamic private schools while the home schools are restricted, and the parents would be forced to send their children to public schools where religious symbols are not allowed to be displayed. In his address, the former French secretary stated that the government is making a law to curb Islamism and communitarian withdrawal. The latter criterion significantly underscores that the French government denounces any legal and political existence of any minorities in its territory, and the state will oppress any effort to build either a cultural or religious identity.

Macron has acknowledged the prevailing marginalisation of French Muslims but has never implemented any policy to address the issue regarding education, health care, and housing. While introducing the Anti-Separatism Bill, Macron claimed the bill's sole purpose was to reinforce French secular values and did not target Muslims. His rhetoric regarding Islam is embedded in the colonial and imperial prejudices against Islam, and he explicitly stated that Islam is a religion in crisis all over the world. He declared his intention to create an enlightened Islam, indicating that Islam is a flawed religion and needs to be reformed by European values. (Käsehage,2021)

Islamic separatism is a threat to French security, but asserting it as a threat to French republican values is problematic. The significant threat is how the government responds to separatism, oppressing minority rights and curtailing religious freedom. The republican values can be protected without harming the minorities, but the crackdown by the French government may result in the further alienation of the Muslim community. After 9/11, Muslims were criticised for being a community

and sustaining a global feeling (Ummah); simultaneously, they were asked to condemn the terrorist activities committed by the radicals as a community (Roy 2015). Introducing the Anti-Separatism Separatist Bill might generate more hatred and alienation of French Muslims, which eventually may lead to more radicalisation as a ramification of the ongoing anti-Islamic legislation and discrimination in the country (Käsehage,2021) By allowing the government authorities to close mosques under any suspicious circumstances, the government undermines the freedom of worship enshrined in Article 1 of the law of Laïcité. The enforcement of the bill undoubtedly excludes the already vulnerable Muslim community, denying them the realm of social visibility and upward mobility, either collectively or individually. (Khemilat 2021)

Muslims are not the first community labelled as separatist in French history. From the French Revolution itself, any effort to recognise or demand a composite identity was met with severe oppression. The term was used for the first time in French political history in 1939 to denote the communists' loyalty to the USSR. It was also used to disown the anti-imperial struggles against French colonialism, particularly those of Algerian people; similarly, the autonomist movements within the French territory were also labelled as separatist. Charles De Gaulle often used the term to quell the dissenting voices against him in his political rhetoric. The current French regime implicitly invokes the prejudices embedded in its colonial past by labelling the Muslim community as separatists. Moreover, it implies that Muslims are the 'Other' of French Nationalism and republican values. (Khemilat 2021)

The Fay Forward

Ramadan (1999) observes that the primary cause of Muslim segregation is the absence of engagement and ability to influence government policy since French Muslims have no umbrella organisation to act as a pressure group and negotiate with the larger political spectrum. He also points out that France's hang-up over its colonial legacy in Algeria embodies the absolute separation of state and religion and underscores the inevitability of the transition from "Islam in France" to "Islam de France". He is very optimistic that French Muslims can benefit from the neutrality of the French state vis-à-vis religion. Linking immigration and Islam undermines the fact that the majority of French Muslims are citizens by

birth, and the political views of Muslims in France are not intertwined by the events in the Middle East but informed by their socio-economic conditions in the country (Laurence & Viasse 2007). They also debunk the myth of religiosity as a critical component of extremism. According to the authors, alienation, isolation and generational crisis make them more vulnerable to fundamentalism. The emergence of a new middle class in the community is also overlooked by embedding social exclusion with religiosity. He also argues that Muslims' beliefs are not contrary to the French Republican ideals like gender equality, democracy, and Laïcité. (Laurence & Viasse 2007).

Based on an ethnographic study, Adidas, Laitin, and Valfort (2016) explain that discrimination is severe in the job market, housing, and other areas of life. The mastery of the language and the hesitation to integrate the Muslims are observed as an impediment to segregation. Regardless of the secular claim, religion is an essential factor in the job market and public behaviour, and most people consider Islam a threat to French society and its Christian values and secular norms. They conclude with the recommendation that religious diversity should be adopted for the fair integration of French Muslims in the wake of growing Islamophobia throughout France.

Oliver Roy, a scholar from France, argues that the radicalisation of European Muslims in general and French Muslims is not linked to the temporary political tussle in the Middle East. Similarly, the immigrants from West Asia and North Africa are not involved in the terrorist attacks; according to him, the main reason for the extremism is the cultural alienation felt by Muslims across Europe, which is a significant challenge and a phenomenon yet to be resolved by assimilation and multiculturalism adopted in both in UK and France respectively. He puts forward the need for European Islam to be separated from cultural elements and monolithic settings, concluding that the concept is poorly understood.

Another challenge is the socio-economic disadvantage of Muslims due to their political inability to exert pressure and the hostility of mainstream society. Muslims in France face considerable discrimination in the job market because of their Muslim identity. The growing Islamophobia in the wake of the September 11 attack and the terrorist attack in France by extremist Muslims culminated in fostering the

antagonist attitude towards Muslims in Europe in general and France in particular. (Fredette 2017) The French government and the intellectuals will engage with the Muslim questions in France, and only a call for pluralistic secularism can integrate Muslims in France completely into the French mainstream society.

Reference

- Adida, Claire L., et al. "Identifying Barriers to Muslim Integration in France." *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, vol. 107, no. 52, 2010, pp. 22384–22390
- Adida, C., Laitin, D., & Valfort, M. (2016). Anti-Muslim Discrimination in the French Labor Market and Its Consequences. *Why Muslim Integration Fails in Christian-Heritage Societies* (pp. 15-28). Cambridge, Massachusetts; London, England: Harvard University Press
- Adida, C., Laitin, D., & Valfort, M. (2016). Beyond France: Muslim Immigrants in Western Europe and in the United States. *Why Muslim Integration Fails in Christian-Heritage Societies* (pp. 127-147). Cambridge, Massachusetts; London, England
- Avramopoulos, Dimitris. 2015. "Discours du Commissaire Dimitris Avramopoulos, lors de la réunion ministérielle internationale à Paris sur Charlie Hebdo, le 11 Janvier 2015." European Commission. January 11. Accessed April 06, 2022. http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release_SPEECH-15-3141_en.htm.
- BBC. 2015. Charlie Hebdo attack: Three days of terror. January 14. Accessed April 05, 2022. <http://www.bbc.com/news/world-europe-30708237>.
2015. "Paris attacks: Millions rally for unity in France." BBC News. January 11. Accessed April 06, 2022. <http://www.bbc.com/news/world-europe-30765824>.
- . 2015. "Paris attacks: Suspects' profiles." BBC News. January 12. Accessed April 08, 2022. <http://www.bbc.com/news/world-europe-30722038>.
- Bowen, J. R. (2009). *Can Islam be French?: Pluralism and pragmatism in a secularist state* (Vol. 30). Princeton University Press.
- El Hamel, C. (2013). *Black Morocco: a history of slavery, race, and Islam* (No. 123). Cambridge University Press.
- Fredette, J. (2014). *Constructing Muslims in France: Discourse, public identity, and the politics of citizenship*. Temple University Press.
- Fredette, J. (2014). Claiming Membership: French Muslim Identities, Political Goals, and Repertoires of Contention. In *Constructing Muslims in France: Discourse, Public Identity, and the Politics of Citizenship* (pp. 47-77). PHILADELPHIA: Temple University Press

Laïcité under pressure: From the Headscarf Ban ... - Perooly

- Ghouse, Mike. 2015. "Angela Merkel Can Prevent Another Charlie Hebdo." The Huffington Post. January 15. Accessed April 06, 2022. http://www.huffingtonpost.com/mike-ghouse/angela-Merkel-can-prevent_b_6470140.html
- Gilbert. J, Keane. D, "How French law makes minorities invisible" theconversation.com. Accessed April 06, 2022 <https://theconversation.com/how-french-law-makes-minorities-invisible-66723>
- Kuru, Ahmet T. "Secularism, State Policies, and Muslims in Europe: Analysing French Exceptionalism." *Comparative Politics*, vol. 41, no. 1, 2008, pp. 1–19
- Laurence, J. (2011). The Emancipation of Europe's Muslims. In *The Emancipation of Europe's Muslims*. Princeton University Press.
- Laurence, J., & Vaisse, J. (2007). *Integrating Islam: Political and religious challenges in contemporary France*. Brookings Institution Press.
- Nielsen, Jørgen. 2007. "The question of Euro-Islam: restriction or opportunity?" In *Islam in Europe: Diversity, Identity and Influence*, edited by Aziz al-Azmeh and Effie Fokas, 34-48. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press
- Rudnicka-Kassem, D. (2016). Searching for a New Identity: Muslims in Western Europe. *Politeja-Pismo Wydziału Studiów Międzynarodowych i Politycznych Uniwersytetu Jagiellońskiego*, 13(44), 251-263.
- Sahill, P. H. (2017). Charlie Hebdo Attack: An Analysis of the Consequences and the Role of Political Islam in the EU. *Jan Masaryk Review of International Studies*, 1(1), 6-22.
- Tibi, Bassam. 2008. *Political Islam, World Politics and Europe: Democratic Peace and Euro- Islam versus Global Jihad*. 1st. Abingdon: Routledge.
- Vidino, Lorenzo. 2011. *Radicalization, Linkage, and Diversity: Current Trends in Terrorism in Europe*. Research Paper, Arlington, VA: RAND Corporation.
- Webster, J. (2007). French identity, Muslim identity: universalism, laïcité, and the Islamic challenge.
- Yahya, Maha. 2015. "What Does the Charlie Hebdo Attack Mean for Europe?" Carnegie Endowment for International Peace. January 15. Accessed April 02, 2015. <http://carnegieendowment.org/syriaincrisis/?fa=57725>.